

Artificial intelligence is improving every day, but at the cost of more and more computing power. Europe needs to be in the race and focus on applications which deliver real social and economic value in Europe, especially in embedded AI.

The AI race

By MARC DURANTON

Artificial intelligence (AI) is everywhere in the news, with personal assistants being one of its most visible expressions. Following the image recognition that drove the renewal of AI in 2012, natural language processing (NLP) is the next “big thing” driving research and competitions. It has surprisingly good results in many areas, mainly with gigantic neural networks (known as “megamodels”) based on “transformers”.

These large networks, exemplified by GPT-3 [1], can be applied in many domains, from generating source code from text specification (OpenAI Codex [2]) to the generation of images (DALL-E [3]) or short videos (Google Imagen Video [4]) from text descriptions. They are also an embodiment of the battle between the US (and between US companies) and China to get the most powerful artificial neural networks.

The new “megamodels” like GPT-3 and its followers show surprisingly interesting performances in many domains, and might be a path towards AGI (artificial general intelligence). However, while some of their results are good, others are meaningless, so all results should be taken with caution and with a critical mindset.

On the other side of the spectrum, deep learning techniques are getting better and better at analysing data from the real world (audio, video, signals), allowing better interaction between computers and the physical world. These techniques (like voice recognition, analysis of images), which previously had to be executed in the cloud, can now be done on embedded systems.

As algorithms are improving, together with better specialized hardware, we can forecast that the “big” models that are running today on large servers will be able to run on edge devices soon, unlocking a lot of new usages. Europe should be at the forefront of this “squeezing” of complex AI models into edge devices.

This section of the HiPEAC Vision explores several aspects of new AI systems:

- “Gigantic Transformers and megamodels: The next El Dorado for AI?” or “Is ‘the bigger, the better’ the path to AGI?”
The new large systems, generally based on transformers, with billions of parameters, show very interesting and surprising results in many areas with the same network, but separating the wheat from the chaff in their results is still a challenge.
- “AI for better integration between the physical and the cyber worlds: Embedded AI”
Extracting valuable information from the physical world and interpreting it opens the way for a lot of new applications like autonomous vehicles, better man-machine interfaces, and smart devices, but the processing should be performed near where the data are created for efficiency reasons.
- “AI as a helper to design better software and hardware”
AI can be used to co-design software; one spin-off of gigantic models such as GPT-3 is their ability to generate code from textual description, opening a new direction for helping programmers. This is already used for Github [5] (Copilot based on OpenAI Codex) for example. In terms of hardware design, AI techniques are used to prune design space exploration to help define optimized architecture, and also to optimize the routing of complex chips.

Key insights

- AI can be classified according to different uses. In this chapter, we focus on some of the most relevant scenarios for the HiPEAC community:
 - Megamodels have a lot of applications, but require enormous computing power, which is becoming less and less affordable and accessible and brings with it a sizeable carbon footprint.
 - AI for better integration between the physical and the cyber world (analysing the environment and proposing decisions).
 - AI as helpers:
 - AI helping to create software: AutoML (automated machine learning) is democratizing the development of applications using deep learning approaches, allowing non-specialists to develop their own applications.
 - AI helping to generate better hardware.
- Of course, AI can and is used in many other application domains, which are outside of the scope of this chapter.
- Megamodels show surprisingly good results in many domains; as such, they could be seen as a path towards AGI. However, they lack common sense and some of their results are pure fantasy. How can we use only the “good” results?
- However, today’s “large” models will be optimized and will be able to run on edge devices in the future due to algorithm improvements, optimization tools (pruning and quantization) and optimized hardware.
- Distribution will allow AI to “learn” through the collaboration of edge devices (federations of devices).
- We are witnessing the emergence of various AI techniques that don’t need very large databases of labelled data (either self-supervised learning techniques, or those which use simulation(s) – virtual environments in the loop to generate data for training). Reinforcement learning approaches, or self-supervised learning techniques, do not need as much data for the learning phase; they only need a reward function or data themselves to provide supervision. They will be increasingly used in applications.

Key recommendations

- Europe should focus on developing embedded AI solutions for better integration/understanding of the physical world, e.g. for near-the-edge and edge devices, (like automotive, smart factories, etc), leveraging its knowhow in cyber-physical systems and embedded systems.
- It is necessary to continue improving the efficiency (in terms of both energy and cost) of the hardware, software and algorithms that are used by deep learning-based AI.
- Europe should not leave the race for the “megamodels” and computing resources need to be available to European researchers and industry to develop European megamodels and experiment with them. Perhaps a “CERN”-like common infrastructure should be promoted?
- Europe should be at the forefront of techniques to move “large” models into edge devices, with tools (pruning networks, using the right data representation (quantization), or other optimization techniques), efficient algorithms and new edge hardware with high performance capabilities and low energy requirements.
- As new learning techniques that need fewer data for learning develop, these algorithms will also be interesting in embedded systems or in on-premises systems. Research in Europe could focus on new approaches that do not require a lot of data for learning, and on federated learning approaches that allow privacy to be preserved.
- AI techniques will be increasingly present as a tool to support the development of software and hardware. These technologies should be evaluated and should trigger the development of new products.
- Research and development of tools helping to identify bias and misbehaviour manifested by AI tools should be developed further. The large models (generally transformer based) show interesting results mixed with nonsense. Solutions to separate the good from the bad should be enforced and learning databases curated. Hybrid techniques (using explicit knowledge to check the results of data driven deep neural networks) are a path to explore.

References

[1] “OpenAI API,” [Online]. Available: <https://openai.com/api/>.

[2] “OpenAI Codex,” [Online]. Available: <https://openai.com/blog/openai-codex/>.

[3] OpenAi, “DALL-E 2,” [Online]. Available: <https://openai.com/dall-e-2/>.

[4] “Google Imagen,” October 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://imagen.research.google/video/>.

[5] “GitHub Copilot,” October 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/features/copilot>.

Marc Duranton is a researcher in the research and technology department at CEA (the French Atomic Energy Commission) and the coordinator of the HiPEAC Vision 2023.

This document is part of the HiPEAC Vision available at hipeac.net/vision.

This is release v.1, January 2023.

Cite as: M. Duranton. The AI race. In M. Duranton et al., editors, HiPEAC Vision 2023, pages 68-69, Jan 2023.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7461851

The HiPEAC project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 871174.

© HiPEAC 2023